

12:30 - 14:00	Session 4: AGN and Black Holes	Chair: Jenny Greene (Princeton)
12:30 - 13:00	4a Invited Talk: Jonelle Walsh (Texas A&M)	Elucidating the Black Hole - Galaxy Connection
13:00 - 13:15	4b Tyrone Woods (NRCC)	The origin of the most massive, high-redshift quasars
13:15 - 13:30	4c Feige Wang (Univ. of Arizona)	Finding the First Luminous Quasars
13:30 - 13:45	4d Andreea Petric (STScI)	Obscured AGN at the Cosmic Noon
13:45 - 14:00	4e Marie Wingyee Lau (UCR)	Probing Feedback and Quasar/galaxy Evolution with Extremely Red Quasars

Session 4 live captioning on Tuesday, 6 October 2020

Hello. Welcome to the second session of the second day of the Roman conference on galaxy formation and evolution in the era of the Nancy Grace telescope. Just a few announcements. First of all, we would like to congratulate the three Nobel winners for physics this year. For those of you who like fun facts, there have only been four women who have won a physics prize, 1.9% of the Nobel laureates. Anyway, congratulations to their efforts and pushing forward our knowledge of black holes observationally and theoretically. Just to remind you that we have a poster session at 2:00 p.m. Those of you who have posters and those of you who are visiting, take advantage of that time to go to slack and interact with the poster presenters. Also we will be having a public lecture at 3:00 p.m. today. Max has posted the link to the YouTube channel for that lecture. This is featuring Jennifer Wiseman who will talk about Nancy Grace Roman, the astronomer, and Julie McEnery who will talk about the Roman telescope. Now I will turn this over to **Jenny Greene** who is this afternoon's chair.

Jenny: Thank you. I'm really excited for a set of talks on black holes in this session. We will have one invited talk from Jonelle Walsh. I will be giving her a warning at 20 minutes to give her a five minute warning and two-minute warning. Also, those of you in the audience with questions please go to the Slack channel and you will see threads for each speaker and then at the end of the session we will have time to ask of the speakers a question. Finally, and then you can use thumbs up for questions if you like or put your own questions in. With that I just want to say on this wonderful day for women who study black holes, I'm excited to hear from **Jonelle Walsh** who is a world leading expert and black hole dynamics. Go ahead.

Jonelle: Thank you. Okay. I'm going to be talking about the connection between galaxies and the black holes. I will discuss the current census we have, outstanding questions and the exciting prospects for gaining insight between black holes and galaxies with future facilities. Black holes preside and every massive galaxy and it's becoming clear that black holes are important components of galaxies. We now have very strong evidence for the presence of black holes including an image from the event horizon telescope from the shadow and the dynamic keys for a black hole we have that comes from our own galaxy where we can track the paths. That is certainly a feat that's worthy of a Nobel prize. Beyond the Milky Way black holes have been dynamically detected in 100 galaxies. Dynamically

detected black holes can be done different ways. You can model the kinematics of stars and the rotation and in some cases black holes have been detected in active galaxies. Dynamically searching for black holes requires high resolution observation that goes to the innermost region of galaxies where the potential dominates. That region is the black hole influence and it's pretty small. For typical supermassive black hole, ten solar masses. The black hole here is roughly ten, such small scales with the current observational facilities, roughly within 100. The space telescope with its great resolution is therefore a fundamental role in detecting black holes over the past 25 years. From the high resolution observation we find the masses of black holes correlate with the large-scale galaxy. This is surprising because the black hole gravitational influence is limited to just the central region of the galaxy. The black hole should not have any impact on the large-scale of those galaxy properties. They are clearly closely connected. There have been a number of relations that have been found over the years, here are some of the well studied relations between the black hole mass and the galaxy mass M_{BH} . These relations defy that somehow black holes and galaxies grow and evolve together, however the exact details of that process are not well understood. Okay. A cosmic sense as a black hole has far-reaching implications for galaxy evolution, but currently it's highly incomplete. That is true for low mass black holes with massive low masses and for high mass black holes with masses above ten to the ninth solar masses. This leads major questions regarding the distribution with host galaxy properties. With the current black hole masses, things like the slope and even the scatter of the relations are just not well established for these high mass black holes. And recent progress though has been done by detecting high mass black holes in the galaxies, but their masses that they possibly lie above that. They are still too few available measurements around to really characterize the scaling relations in this upper end. The uncertainties are equally severe at the opposite end where low mass black holes appear to exhibit large relations. And new measurements and low mass early type galaxies also show signs of deviations below the scaling relations. Another issue is that dynamical black hole mass measurements have a need and galaxies that are not representative of the local galaxy population. On one of these plots I am showing, the galaxies size, effective radius and the galaxy, the green points on this plot are showing galaxies with published black hole mass measurements. The point here is that they dynamical black hole mass measurements have been made in a wide set of galaxies adding luminosity, galaxies with small relative to a nearby galaxy populations have been preferentially targeted. However, sampling of the luminosity parameter is really important. As you move away from that point that we have been measuring, numerous galaxy properties change, things like stellar block, the ratio, gas content, stellar populations, and morphology. Also, galaxies that grow in different ways and end up different regions of this plots. Clearly we need to do a better job of sampling the parameter space in order to obtain a more complete census of black holes and a wider range of galaxies that have experienced diverse growth. Our knowledge of how black holes are connected as they are, but there still a lot to be learned. It's incomplete and we still don't have a good understanding of primary physical mechanisms that drive the empirical correlation. We need more black hole mass measurements and order a wider range of galaxies that have grown through different channels. Moreover, other fundamental questions remain unanswered so as a few examples, few black holes and galaxies grow over time, or does the growth to the black hole proceed that to the galaxy or vice versa? Are there black holes in the galaxy and in the Milky Way in the globular clusters? How do they form? Where are their initial seed to masses and how can they acquire so much mass so quickly after the Big Bang? With the rest of the talk I will highlight some advances that have allowed us to these -- to address some of these questions and then what future facilities can do for us. It's played an important role in detecting black holes over the past two decades. More recently though significant progress has been made using adaptive optics. It can deliver similar resolutions, but has the added advantage of being used with larger telescopes and it operates in the near infrared. Therefore galaxies that were previously pretty tough to observe because they were too faint or too dusty can be studied in great detail. As a result they have contributed some of the most massive and least and least massive black hole masses ever made and everything in between. This includes studies of galaxies with several billion solar mass black holes down to the low mass, early galaxies. Given the extensive observational and effort involved in a single determination the approach that has been used for years and the field is to study one or a few black holes at a time. Advancing the field forward also requires examining large homogeneous data sets of carefully selected examples. One survey was conducted with AO, they are producing 25 dynamical black hole masses with galaxies that were selected to explore the poorly populated regions of the black hole scaling relation. That includes high dispersion, early type galaxies, low dispersion, and remnants. We are also carrying out a large black hole program using Gemini North. We were awarded 253 hours to measure black hole masses using methods and 31 galaxies using the graph assisted by adaptive optics. I showed this plot earlier and highlighted how the current measurements in green have been made for galaxies who are not representative and the population shown by the gray contours. Our program is aimed at entrusting the troubles and bias. Here in red are the galaxies and our example. They significantly increase coverage of this important parameter without sampling that well

populated region within the dotted oval. The galaxies in our example span a wide range of properties by design. For example, 60-300 kilometers per second, it contains a number of spiral galaxies who nearly doubled the number of measurements made which really happens in widely explored dynamical technique. So far we've contained completed observations were 12 of the galaxies and of those 12 galaxies already enhance the diversity of black hole hosts. We've observed the largest galaxy in the example as well as the lower luminosity example with affected radii. Here I'm showing some example of the spectra for the galaxy that we have observed. The data quality here really is excellent. From the absorption line we can map out the kinematics as a function of location and that is what is being shown here. The velocity map shows that both of these galaxies are rotating and of the velocity dispersion map shows a dramatic rise in the dispersion as you move into the nucleus. Values at about 370 and 60 kilometers per second for the two galaxies. Again, really highlighting the wide range of galaxies we have in our sample. We've also found some interesting cases. This is a repeating edge on early type galaxy, where there is a decrease and the velocity dispersion at the nucleus. That drop could imply the nondetection of a black hole which would still be interesting since that would mean the galaxy lies well below both the current and relations. The stigma drop could result from a distinct dynamically cold start in the nucleus. Our dynamical models will be able to provide more information and distinguish between those scenarios. Besides the AO observations, and three filters, we've observed nearly all the galaxies with the field graph and even wider field only 2.7-meter telescope at McDonald's. We are constructing orbit based dynamical models are the main idea is the gravitational potential consists of contributions and black hole stars and dark matter. He stellar potential is determined from seeking the image and projecting it, a viewing orientation and multiplying by a mass ratio. We then set that up. We find new orbit such that the position matches the observed kinematics and the brightness from the image. And then we calculate a whole bunch of different models with interest like the black hole mass and we are looking for a model that most closely matches the data. When we do that for one of the galaxies, we find the black hole mass at 2.3 times town to the ninth. You are seeing the comparison with the two observations in the model and green. With her black hole mass, it is consistent, but it clearly lies above that spirit that is even using the total luminosity. It turns out that PGC look similar to other outliers from the mall relation that are shown in red here. All these galaxies have small sizes, so effective radii at 1-3 or luminosity is between 10-11. That corresponds to stellar mass is about -- and they have a large dispersion. These local compact galaxies host massive black holes, but they're very different from the kinds of galaxy you would expect to find at the upper end of the black hole relation. Instead of looking like the elliptical, 1275 in the right image, the compact galaxies look quite similar to the red shift galaxy. Since the local compact galaxies look similar, they could be relic. There red nuggets are thought to grow in size and mass through a series of mergers to reduce the typical early type galaxies of today. Perhaps our example of local compact galaxy took a different pathway, the outskirts of their galaxies. Given their over a massive black holes, the local compact galaxies could suggest the growth would be better. In addition to telescopes we now also have these wide-field highly sensitive IFU's. They're very good at providing efficient way to hunt for the most massive black holes. Yep to search for them over larger differences and you'd expect to find them in the higher galaxy which has that. The lower mass elliptical galaxies tend to have rising light profiles. Like the gray lines that are shown in the plots. The more massive elliptical galaxies often have a deficit at the center which is shown by the redlines. It is quite challenging to attain the high noise needed to measure the stellar kinematics in the galaxy centers. As an example, home Holm 15a, it is fainter than any of the previous of the massive early type galaxies, but they have been dynamically modeled so far. Despite the faint core, with one hour, they were able to get the high signals that they needed to measure the stellar kinematics over this one field. And one applying stellar dynamical models they find a black hole mass. It host one of the largest dynamically determined black hole masses to date. The stellar dynamical models are quite a powerful tool beyond to getting the black hole mass. You can also learn about the galaxies distribution and history. Based on this increasingly orbit within the core, along with the let profile, they find that it is consistent with being a merger reminiscent of two other earlier galaxies that already had these pre-existing cores themselves. Beyond the observational improvements with AO, there been recent efforts to improve the stellar dynamical models themselves. A couple of new codes have recently been developed. Almost all the stellar dynamical black hole masses so far have been measured assuming access imagery. Being able to explore it is important for modeling features. Going forward, these codes will certainly have an impact on both the upper and lower end of the black hole relation. In addition there been an improvement to existing codes like feeding them up and updating orbital, not just based on the observed stellar kinematics, but combining information about stellar populations. King over to measurements, up until a few years ago almost all the black hole measurements from modeling rotating disks were done so using HST observations of ionized gas. Molecular gas from radio observations offer an alternative. The dynamical modeling with gas precipitates and the cold, dense gas is likely to have less turbulent motion then the warmer ionized gas. One of the major systematic associated with gas

dynamical modeling may be much less of a concern with radio observation. Also the data cubes we get from a radio provide better spatial coverage of the gas themselves. That's especially compared to some of the earlier observations where you are getting a handful of spectra from a few. With this increased coverage of the disk you can get better constrain the position angle and the inclination angle which have an impact on the inferred. For the first ever black hole mass measurement made from CO emissions came several years ago using the karma. In this case the black hole influence was just barely resolved even though this is a really nearby galaxy. It would require ten hours to complete. It opened up a new way to measure black hole masses. Since then, ALMA has provided super sensitivity. It gets precision black hole mass measurements to advance the field. There's been a pretty big uptick in the number of black hole masses over the last couple of years and now the number of molecular black hole mass measurements is about equal to the ionized gas that everyone has done before. With ALMA we are now able with the low and high black holes. I had been a part of the collaboration using ALMA to measure them in this way. Observations of early type galaxies at the upper end of the relation, selecting them based on the imaging, suggesting that there will be nicely rotating gas presence. Our program -- thank you. Our programs combined with some other data and the archive really do show that there are a number of promising targets for molecular dynamical modeling. You are seeing some examples here. On the left are the distributions of the dash the distributions of these and then on the right are the radial velocity maps. Again, really highlighting the opportunity that ALMA has given us to take an accurate census of black holes. For the gas dynamical modeling, we have this rotating gas disk. We determined the circular velocity based on the mass which depends on the black hole mass, the stellar light distribution and the ratio. We set up a model of velocity field on a subsample of bread and we project that onto the sky for a given value. the intrinsic line profile are soon to be Guassian and then are centered on that grid. After we've go back to the pixel scale, we directly compare the model cubes to the observed queue. We are searching for the best combination of parameters. As an example, this is 30 to 58, a nearby elliptical galaxy. We got ALMA cycle to observations and it showed that there was very clearly control high velocity omission, but the upturns and the velocity diagram were not that well resolved. So he went back and got .1 second resolution data and this highly resolved the potential gas kinematics. In the upturn in the position diagram are very, very clear. We fit rotating disk models to the data and we found a high mass black hole with a mass of 2.2 times ten to the ninth, but the uncertainty of just .2%, estimated systematic uncertainty of 6%. This is the most precise black hole mass measurement for any early type galaxies so far and arrival some of the major black holes in spiral galaxies. With the last few minutes I will look forward to the future and what we will be able to do with the facility in the era of the Nancy Grace Roman telescope. One of the questions I pose at the start of the talk was whether black souls and galaxies grow in lockstep with one another? In other words, if there is evolution in the relations. Currently we can't directly answer this question using dynamical mass measurements. If the best we can do is answer that question and directly, say by trying to find relics of galaxies like perhaps those local compact galaxies, or by estimating black hole masses using the broad lines. Unfortunately with these indirect methods they're just conflicting results, and selection bias can lead to false edification of evolution and the relation. The facilities will be able to answer the question more directly so we can dynamically measure black hole masses and various red shift bins and compared to the local relations parade this is best accomplished with the high mass black holes. For example, with the telescope and optics, we will be able to resolve the expected black hole influence of the solar mass throughout the universe. Of course you still need to worry about getting high enough signal to do the measurement, that's obviously an important point. The resolution for these high mass black holes are no longer a concern. We can also search for dynamical signatures of intermediate black holes. There have been some hands dynamically for intermediate black holes in clusters and a low mass galaxies, both late type galaxies and early type galaxies. The results are highly controversial, often due to issues with spatial resolution and sensitivity. Studying intermediate black holes is really important since it forms or ideas of how they form. For example, if the initial black hole comes from direct collapse of gas in the early universe, the expectation is that black holes distribution will cut off the low value, perhaps ten to the fourth, and we also expect that these will be rare to have lower occupation fractions today. Future facilities will be sensitive to the dynamical signatures of solar mass black holes and ten to the fourth of solar mass black holes up to 3-5. With the Nancy Grace Roman telescope, is a great way to find the best target for these detailed dynamical studies, and that's especially true for tracking the red shift evolution and the scaling relations. Since were talking about using the rare, highest mass galaxies and black holes. Also the imaging will provide resolution over galaxy skills needed for the modeling and we can also potentially study environmental dependence on black hole growth which really hasn't been explored. I'm out of time. I will leave this up and take questions.

Awesome. Thank you for this excellent talk. There is a lot of enthusiasm. I will have time for two questions. I will take one that has the most thumbs. Could you say a bit more about how, how you're working towards an unbiased population of black holes? Is that just based on a selection, a different selection of host galaxies or is there another selection you need to do to get an unbiased view of the black holes themselves?

That's a really good question. This is definitely a hard game to play. What we did is we were actually kind of all surprised when we looked at that luminosity sized parameter, that plot that I showed. Kind of the, what people had been thinking about doing is focusing on the current scaling relations. You take ML, what point do we need, but really going to this luminosity parameter space. There's just so many different properties, galaxy properties that vary as we move along that space. I think collecting in that space really is going to help us to try and push to do the regions that have been unexplored. Ed is difficult. We are now doing difficult galaxies. There are a number of spiral galaxies here and they come with a whole host of challenges and issues, but it's worth at this time pushing it.

Another question. I know you've thought about this, comment briefly for now about enter comparisons between different methods. There is one question about, if the mass, and how different techniques agreed? And of course that's another context.

Again, another important point. That's another area that are field needs to start thinking about but it's not just about measuring another black hole mass, but understanding the sample under systematic systematic in each of the methods. All of this come of the dynamical methods, they do have their own systematic, but they're different. It's important to compare them. Unfortunately it just has not been done on a large number of galaxies. I would say a kind of more focusing on stellar versus gas, there's only been a handful, maybe six or seven so far. That's been helped by ALMA, so getting more gas dynamical is something that is, it has been really helpful. And unfortunately with these small numbers it's hard to say what the impact is on black hole scaling relations. Unfortunately things don't look like they tend to agree, so there are a couple of cases that do agree. The majority of cases, the stellar dynamical mass, by factors of like 2-4. Those are great because they give you very precise measurements, but you need special conditions and those are rare. They're hard to find unfortunately. It's definitely something that the field needs to work on.

Awesome. Thank you for a beautiful talk.

I think we are going to move on **Tyrone Woods**.

Tyrone: Thank you for having me. Thank you for a great talk at a great lead. I want to drill down, down into it further. In particular, the high universe and problems like this. You'll hear more about this later today. We now know that there are -- it is possible to build quasar's, a billion years in the event to other facilities we know -- 200 or so really amazing quasars. They have been able to build up. This is a problem. And it brings us to this dilemma. If you want to try and grow a typical, low mass, top three relatively, something that could result from stars -- and build that up into a billion, you could have it born at the very beginning of the universe and go right up until the red shift and you could may be just barely get there, probably not really. How do we get around that? One idea, of course, if you look at the growth in that .1 coefficient, we could try and go -- and relief get them to black hole quickly. The top three stars, black holes, they are -- top three stars are both liable to be very strong. This is bad news if you want to increase a lot of the gas around you. Furthermore, these are going to be born in clusters, massive objects. And the interactions are likely to kick a number of them out, all making for a initial seat up to a larger mass. The other idea is to look at the seed mass is that we see and instead try to knock off a few, but invoke a 10⁻⁴, 10⁻⁵ solar mass black hole seed. This is the massive seed. What we need when we talk about massive seeds, it can be a couple of different things, classical idea in the 70s and 80s is to look at the rapid collapse of a dense cluster of stars in the early universe, into a single object. More recently, you might be able to merge gas Proto galaxies and produce some sort of collapsing gas cloud at the center. I think that the most widely advocated, something for which the evidence is growing, what we call a direct collapse. This is an idea that has evolved over the years, go back to the 60s, 70s, 80s. Alongside that there been a number of different ideas that I've evolved over the year, how we would actually produce a 10⁻⁴, 10⁻⁵. I think the leading idea now is one way or the other producing what we call an atomic halo. If you have two halos, one primary

halo and a dense environment. Let's start with synchronized for now. One is further along, it's contraction to presentation, out at red shift, 15, before the ionization. Our initial, slightly further will condense, contract, fragment and give us the population. The ionizing radiation is going to stay trapped close to the source. . They can stream freely from this halo and under the right conditions can completely destroy the molecular hydrogen. This has important news for that halo because in the absence of metals, it was your primary coolant. Now instead of relatively low temperatures leading to a typical top three stellar population and presentation, our halo was going to contract and heat up until it can activate atomic in the neighborhood of 8,000. What this means is that they will get up to around 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} . For what we expect, they will scale up 2.1 solar mass. The loan is to build the astounding objects. What are they actually going to look like? To sum up of a whole bunch of studies together over the last decade or so, the answer is emphatically not a 10^{-5} solar mass quietly collapses within a black hole at the snap of the finger. You are going to produce a rather long-lived complicated object, a super massive protostar, a fluffy, radiated. It's going to survive for 100,000 years. And collapse while still burning hydrogen, it will survive beyond 2-4. Here we found, going back to the study, for the first time a direct relation. You will see our most important initial condition under direct collapse. And our final cloud, potentially the first step towards building initial direct cloud black hole function which is the vital importance if we want to find the leftovers of these processes that don't make it all the way to supermassive sizes. But really out of maybe -- two key takeaways I want people to remember. These objects are long-lived. This is actually the case, even if we look beyond the direct model to things like Proto galaxy, massive Proto galaxy or just if we look to things of a more classical idea, the collapse of a cluster. No matter what we do it's very hard to think it is in going to live for a long time. That means we need to go hunting for it. Which is where I put on my recovery theorist cap and talk about how we can prop together a number of people, much better at us and advising material strategy and trying to go hunting for these to come up with the best ways to try and -- a way we could observationally confirm that this is really how the direct model proceeds. How we can actually form a massive seed. Of course a number of ideas have been perceived, we heard about trying to find a low mass seed, nearby and of course trying to find black holes that are over massive and the host of galaxies. All of these come with some ambiguities because we don't really get to trace the whole history. One thing that I think is going to be almost a slam-dunk is these direct collapse black holes on the more common side if they form the majority of supermassive black holes. Then their formation rate, like the blue curve, upper blue curve that you see here, and a minor detail that is not so minor, most of these halos are going to produce a single object, but they're either going to lead to mergers which are going to give us -- mergers which can be detectable by observatories. Out too much greater redshifts that we would expect from the normal buildup from hierarchal mergers of black holes. Of course there is an awful lot of uncertainty in exactly where they ought to be. You can look at the red curve, the only form of the very most massive. The behemoth in the higher red shift universe. 2 minutes. Perfect. If we're on a more common end of things, this is a typical challenge then actually want to model, one way to go and test this is to look for the supermassive objects directly before they collapse into black holes. If they're up on the more common side then you should be able to find one integrated, somewhere integrated alongside. -- in that case he will be able to find them. If on the other hand we do know what these objects look like, but they're not nearly as common as we had thought, then it's going to take some doing. I think that in this case actually there is a uniquely cool thing at the Roman telescope, if you look at something like the very cool ultra deep Field and try to hunt to these things, haunts for these objects somewhere around the peak of where we think they might be forming. It should be doable for us. Designing a survey that can actually take out likely candidates for the follow-up is going to be the trick. Combined with the other methods for hunting black holes, you will hear about it later this session, I think very soon, within the next decade using next-generation facilities, we will be able to make a statement, at the very least, whether it is a formation super mass. I will stop there.

Thank you. Thank you for a nice talk. We do have a question and slack. Basically I have time for a want and you answer the rest. The question really is, do we expected imprints on black hole scaling relations from different models?

An imprint? Differences in heavy? I think the answer would be looking at the today, not really, but going back to high red shift, you should be able to find these objects we are very much over mass.

Thank you. And there is some other questions there. I think we have to move on to the next. Thank you. Take it away.

Feige Wang: I'm at the University of Arizona. Today I will talk about quasars with the telescope. Before speaking on that I would like to first tell you why we care about quasars. I will move on to give a brief overview of the surveys and finally to, how to find with telescope. First of all, quasars is hosting an active black hole and the method of galaxies -- in principle if you can find the earliest supermassive black hole or the earliest quasars you can change the black hole history. On the left, all the quasars, about seven here and most of them have mass -- if you look at the red line and the purple line, 7.5. This is produced by the direct -- going higher and higher quasars we can put a stronger on the black hole. The massive galaxy, quasars, we can -- currently most have the measurement of the black hole mass, but anyway, based on this luminous quasars with over mass of most of the galaxy, of the black holes, this is based on the luminous quasars. We want to go more towards the perimeter space to see whether they are really different relating. Okay. The other thing, the cosmic reorganization, we can gather high-quality and the quasars we can see a lot of features that imprint the medium by looking at those features we can -- the universe is highly -- also we can see those transmitted spikes by measuring the meters and -- if you go to a higher, we can see the proximity around here, if you zoom in and here you can see the observer spectrum is different from the predicted spectrum because it is significant, you add the peak with the red over the map is significant. You can see a lot of here, you can use it as a high -- eventually we only know several quasars and here you can see there is a large scatter here. It is because we have proven different -- and we need a large sample to make a better understanding of how it looks like. The first question, how do you find them? In the past few years there are several surveys, you will find six here and trying to improve the understanding -- and the focus -- the quasars malfunctioning, this is field imaging is mostly by the Subaru surveys and the way the quasars around six and absolute around 22. We have a good understanding of the quasars close to the galaxies. The other focus is how to get higher resolution, .5. How it evolves, it was higher. Those higher quasars, you need a wide field imaging survey and in the last few years there are many different imaging surveys allowing us to search those high Rez quasars and with the magnitude of 21, the absolute magnitude of about minus 25 or so. Based on those imaging data we have now, we have a statistic sampling. In the last couple of years we have about six, 6.5 with quasars, and three around 7.5. And here, the red and magnitude, the red dots are the surveys and the black dots are from other surveys. We have three quasars at really high, and one is here, so it's actually over here. And now we have a relative complete sample with 6.5, so based on this part we can -- comparing it to six, quasars, that line here. If you integrate the function we can find it is bright around 26 corresponding to -- if you assume increasing. It seems it is no longer following in the infrared. It is decreasing which means there are less and less quasars high rising. If you -- following this decline, there are only -- by comprising the -- it is from Torp's and early galaxies. You can see other magnitudes higher than quasars. How you can find them, it's really wide imaging in the infrared. And the most features to distinguish those different -- because it has observed the most from the map. You can see the feature and the color and here I show some color parts with the telescope, with the surveys which allows us to search and increase beyond 6.50. Here is the quasars and all that happens. If you want to search higher, we really need higher, which will be available with the telescope to allow us to find quasars. In other color diagrams it's not a distinguished from other. Which means we cannot use the -- the Roman Space Telescope, they are limited. As I said, we can search the increase because the survey has six or so and it has 25 magnitude. Based on the malfunction we measured, about 100 quasars. This allowed us to make a really large, gives us a large sample to allow us to start to the model to the cosmic history. Around eight and nine we needed a telescope -- around eight and we can find quasars around nine. I put a question here because we cannot allow them from seven or nine. We probably can find the rest of nine, but increasing to higher -- if we have been with and we use its we can find even more quasars. We are currently, we are limited. 2 minutes. I really want to highlight that quasars tracing large scale over density because it is residing in the method galaxies and massive halos. In principle you can find the galaxies. In the past there are plenty surveys, but limited by the dash there is no -- we will provide wide field image which will allow us to study the quasars and finally to understand if they are with massive halos or not. I will leave my summary here and will be happy to take any questions.

Wonderful. Thank you. I think people are still may be typing. I will start with a question. I wonder if you thought at all, I believe there's going to be a supernova field. I have this fantasy that variability may help us get even further down the luminosity function. I wonder, with Roman, if you thought about that at all.

I can help for finding low quasars, but were high, the scale is very long. The supernova field is also small field so you will have to get one in the small field. Yeah.

Okay. I think that's all. I think we will just thank you again for a really nice talk. If questions arise please to put them in the slack and we will move on.

Okay. Obscured AGN.

Andreea Petric: Thank you. With no further ado I will summarize my talk. The study of galaxy evolution is the study of black hole evolution and from radio have revealed that the host of AGN are different in significant ways than the host of non-AGN. If you look at it in a specific way which I will show here. What we need to progress, what we don't know our where did all the black holes come from? How exactly are they affecting their AGN host? And is the effect on a certain part of the host for example, the medium, does not translate to an evolution of the entire host? For example, the star formation properties and the history. To do that we need of course the Roman telescope and we also need the variety of multi-wavelengths and in particular I will focus on future multi -- massive multiplied, the next generation. Galaxies have revealed that, and by other telescopes, have revealed that galaxies come in many shapes and colors, but what we find every time with sufficient velocity resolution and spatial resolution is for a massive galaxy, more than that, there is a correlation between the host and the black hole. And while you can establish that correlation from only merger alone, its risk is more than a measurement error and make come from something from the exchange of energy between the central black hole and the rest of the whole galaxy. Where, when, and how were all the black holes formed? This requires a census. Census for the earliest part of AGN, with the arrival of Spitzer, they have been revealed. And following those populations as a functional red shift, what was found with her evolution seem to differ in the plot on the right I show you an example of AGN extracted from Spitzer field determined by looking at the infrared colors and with ground infrared spectroscopy. What you can see is different color lines have different, apparently different evolutionary shapes, but also that we don't have enough information. That is particularly sad because one more galaxies have grown both their host as well as their central supermassive black hole. Of course the conclusion of this is that we need a better understanding, or measurements of the resolution of the sources. The Roman mission is going to be fantastic at finding such sources of both because of its sensitivity in the field as well as the shallower ones that will be able to cover and find peculiar sources. But also because of the green. I will argue that the resolution is not sufficient to do a number of studies that make relevance, such problems like the star formation history, or separating from the various kinematic components. Though studies are important to understand the connection between the central black hole on the host galaxy. We see this evolution of different sources and what we also see is the sources, and by we, studies done and 2015, some of the most obscure quasars look like that mergers, at a red shift. Unfortunately only a handful of those have been so far discovered. And we as I mentioned, we also do this correlation between black hole. We have a need where connecting, the star formation and the galaxy to match the properties of galaxies that we observe. A picture that satisfied a large number of those is that in which mergers trigger a black hole growth and in that process, AGN to come up the evolutionary of mergers. To properly understand this scenario and connect it to the simulation, one needs a high number of galaxies. I should mention that in relations now, like for example, they are fantastic at giving a product that is similar to what they actually observed. And so one of the things that we can check for this scenario is what does it impact that AGN have on galaxies? And if it is challenging -- May be easier. We have observed what they look at and, by looking at everything which has the abstracts, from galaxies, from Spitzer including Starburst. With all those examples together we looked at the AGN contributions from the luminosity, and using red shift, only looking at the red shift, we also looked at this. Here they show the various color color infrared's ways to figure out which ones are the AGN's. Basically it is connected to the fact that an AGN can both increase the infrared continuum and also destroy ionized. What we found, this also has been found before, but not with the statistical significance of adding all of the sources. With that h2 host, this was not a merger affect. At least for the red shift of 0.1. And that the dust features span a wider set of properties in AGN hosts. When looking at optical spectrum from that, we found that this H2 excess was associated with ionized gas. Okay. We have a sample. And without that we cannot yet tell if it is represented, entire population, entire distributional merger grade we found that at least the warm gas and in the warm was different. That just means the AGN is capable of affecting the star formation history. One way to look at that is to have ground-based, optical special results. And so we picked a small sample of the most nearby AGN's that are wearing that and have one. If that happens it should happen with the sources. This work is being done by undergraduates and the results are up luminary. What we do seem to find our incredible rich kinematic system and ionized gas. And if we

were to put those sources than the kinematic features, the profile will be similar to the high velocity and red quasars. One minute? One and a half. So with that we will be able to find more candidates and again with x-ray and radio emission, we will be able to find the most secure sources. And radio emission -- radio service will also help us identify the sources between radio and quasars feedback, but morphologies and broad, low velocity resolution are important especially given the good resolution that it will provide. It does need to be with high velocity resolution, and by high I mean 3,000, kilometers per second -- 3,000 resolution to be able to trace the kinematics and do all of the diagnostics required for star formation history and the impact on the host galaxy. I will conclude with the case for the explorer and in particular, this slide that compares MSE with other missions. With no further ado I will take questions.

Thank you. Still waiting for questions. When you think about having an optical spectrum and I guess a broadband like you were laying out, what is the first paper you want to write once you have that sample?

The star formation histories of AGN hosts are dramatically different or the same. As a nonAGN host. I mean, star formation history, but I think it's both a star formation histories in the context of obviously finding stellar masses, comparing apples to apples. I started the talk by telling you that different AGN's appeared to have a different evolution. In a luminosity function. Is the spectrum going to give you anything in that case? If it seems really obscure?

That's an excellent point. It depends on the sensitivity. And it depends on what red shift we are going. So far, the expected, you know, sensitivity for one hour -- -- [indistinct] --

My bias is that it would may be, the origins would clarify this.

Thank you so much for a really thought-provoking talk.

We are going to go on to the last of the session now from **Marie Wingyee Lau**.

Marie: I hope you are already convinced that quasars are interesting. I am presenting to you, I am at Riverside. This is in collaboration with a graduate student at UC Riverside, Professor Hamann. The topic begins with introducing obscure quasars. And there's this unique population of them known as extremely red quasars. I will talk about what we know about the extremely red quasars and since they are interesting, finally I will talk about science to discover ERQs. Next page. Quasars are a supermassive black hole. They have the evolution of their host galaxies. On the right, it comes the Hopkins paper and showing three intermediate stages and popular evolution models. The models predict black holes growing and obscuring, they grow deep inside the Galactic starburst which is the top stage of the figure. The supermassive black hole grows until a blowout of gas and they reveal a luminous quasars and the galactic nucleus which is the bottom figure. Obscured quasars are the metal stage, they are red and they might appear during this transition blowout phase. Our team discovered a unique population obscure quasars, they are discovered in BOSS and WISE surveys. There are different populations of obscured quasars selecting and producing different brightness criteria. For ERQs in particular we select them based on extremely red colors across the mid infrared. This figure in the middle of the page shows the distributions. The black curve which is the curve is for the extremely red Quasars. The two higher curves, green and blue are luminous Quasars. The lower comes in different colors, the other right and Quasars. The extremely red Quasars have a very distinct distribution that is alike to galactic nuclei. The EL Q is flat across despite being extremely red from infrared. Next page. The figure on the left shows the optical spectra of the example, extremely red Quasars. If you are familiar, they should look peculiar to you. On top of each panel with composites, look at the comparison. The extremely red Quasars is low composite, normalized to have the same continuum level in those panels. This is to highlight how extreme the omission line properties are extremely red Quasars drive fast outflows, a thousand kilometers per second. Because of the iconic physics, the region is composed away from the Quasar. The outflows, we try to look for correlations between the luminosity's or between other properties paired we found that the extreme outflow depends only on color. The figure on the right shows the color versus the velocity of luminous quasars. The stars are luminous blue quasars. The velocity with red color, we got a similar result if we plot color versus velocity shift. Okay. Next page. You see all three outflows have the scales and they are by color. Now larger scales at that, we observed large quasars. An example is shown here. The last image is optimally extracted image of the Ly α halo surrounding it. The function subtracted from the image. The extent

and the luminosity is similar to a luminous, blue quasars. We only found differences and they surface brightness between these ERQs and blue quasars. That means the concept channels to escape despite the observation. This is consistent with a patchy scenario which also explains the distribution being flat. The middle image is a velocity map of the flux and of the dispersion. You can see that most of the extended gas is close to the system and it shows no signs of disturbed kinematics. While there are extremely fast outflows at the scales, fast-moving speeds are not found on certain galactic skills. If extremely red quasars or young quasars, may be the outflows do not have enough time to reach their medium or are -- the outflows may be slows down as they travel through the medium of their host. The other interesting thing to note is that the heavy observation acts, it allows the innermost regions of the halo, which is not possible with blue quasars. I hope you find it interesting, but for a broader understanding of active galactic nuclei we need to search for optically fainter quasars. The first significant for doing that is to go for lower luminosity's. The red quasars, they have always looked at the most luminous quasars which are rare and unusual. If we want to circulate, speculate that all quasars go through that phase, all quasars have had compact, we need to see the problem of luminosity to verify that. The population and the general galaxy. The second significant for finding fainting quasars as to go for writer colors. Maybe they are more -- maybe they are in the earlier stage, may be they have properties that are more extreme or different from their current sample of ERQs. For example they may have different outflow properties. And the differences may form as an evolutionary sequence. And we know that some obscure quasars are missing at high redshifts. The current example of ERQs are found using Epilog's, it's about 22 and we need to go deeper than that to find deeper quasars. The symmetric surveys, currently there is surveys and they wish magnitudes of about 24. There is also the hyper supreme Subaru strategic program, and which it is 26. A 2. color, we can find them more reliably using the full characteristics. For now in the infrared we have two kits, -- from the current example of ERQs. This is where the Roman survey will be useful as we can limit the magnitude of 28. 2 minutes. Okay. Now we are using the all-white catalog for that data. There is an wise catalog, sources, there is the catalog which measures proper motions of the sources so they can help exclude round off from the Quasar. After finding these quasars, we may follow up, it is great for observing and we can measure the kinematics. We already did optics on some of the ERQs. An example is shown in this figure. It shows the image region is compact and is not much larger. In summary, obscure quasars, they are interesting, we are characterizing them and we should find more of them using the metric surveys, the Roman surveys. I'm here to solicit suggestions on strategies for discovering more extremely rare quasars. Thank you.

Wonderful. Under a time. Nice talk. We have a question here. Do you have constraints on the sizes or scales of the Apache obscuring ERQ? Are they small clouds or larger clouds farther out?

This is a good question. There is a paper that tried to measure the relative polarization for the omission line of the ERQs. They found that the dusty region is probably cospatial with the broad emission lines region. That paper is claiming, it's estimating a size. I think that could also just be that the region could be more extensive than normal quasars. Maybe even the region are more extended and there at hundreds on the scale.

I think that, with that lovely talk, that's a conclusion of our session on black holes and galaxies and Roman. I want to thank all the speakers again for a really lovely session. Say goodbye for now.

Thank you. Thanks for chairing this session. Once again, thank you all, the speakers of the session. Thank you all for attending this session. Max has a few reminders for you. And then we will see you tomorrow morning at 10:00 a.m. Eastern for session five. Take it away.

Max: We will have a virtual poster session. I direct you to slack where there is a separate channel for each poster. There is a nice summary as well where you can peruse titles and authors very quickly. If you click through you will see that each poster has its own channel. Posters and lightning talks are there. We encourage authors to be there, but of course you don't have to be. You can take questions at any time. Over the next hour we encourage you to do that.

Last announcement today, we are very excited to offer a Public Lecture as a part of this conference week. That is going to be occurring at 3:00 p.m. Eastern time, one hour from now, and not broadcast here. That will be broadcasted

on YouTube. I posted the link in the announcements channel on slack. I encourage you to check out the lecture. We are very excited to have two speakers from the Goddard Space Flight Center. We will have a Jennifer Wiseman who is the Hubble Project Scientist who will be talking about Nancy Grace Roman. Why she is considered the Mother of Hubble, and why it's so appropriate that our space telescope was named after her. And then we will have Julie McEnery, the Roman Project Scientist, talking about the space telescope and it's science goals. I hope you can join us for that. I'll be signing out now until tomorrow. Join us for posters for the next hour. The public lecture in one hour. We will see you in the morning. Bye-bye, everybody. Thank you all.

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